

LABORATORY DIAGNOSIS OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENCE WITH HEMORRHAGIC VASCULITIS

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The purpose of the study : to determine the changes in the endothelium in patients with hemorrhagic vasculitis.

Material and methods . The study included 60 patients aged 9 to 15 (average age 12 ± 2.5) years with clinical sign of hemorrhagic vasculitis. According to the severity of the disease, 2 main groups of patients: First group patients with a mild course of the disease ($n=22$), second group patients with severe course ($n=23$). The control group consisted of 15 practically healthy equal children of the same age and sex. To achieve the goal of the study in all children the main and control groups were studied functional and structural state of the vascular stand the wall, namely: the thickness of the intima complex media of the common carotid artery by ultrasound duplex scan in the distal third common carotid artery.

Results. Among the total number of children with hemorrhagic vasculitis prevailed boys (60 and 36 %, respectively $p=0.016$). Have more of the examined children (51.8%) were diagnosed with skin articular form, in (22.5 %) skin articular with abdominal syndrome, in 13.3 children of main group established as skin form disease and in 12.2% of children with skin form with abdominal and renal syndromes.

Measuring the thickness of an OCA and CMM as an indicator functional and structural state of the vascular endothelium showed that in children of the 2nd group in the acute period of the disease was recorded correct, the highest result in comparison with the group control - 0.9 (0.82-1.0). In children of the 1st groups the indicators remain at the level of normal - 0.59 (0.52-0.68). When determining these indicators during the improvement period, it was found that in children with mild course of HV IMT thickness OSA remains at the normal level relative to children in the control group 0.50.

Summary In this study, positive changes were observed in the carotid arteries of patients with hemorrhagic vasculitis during treatment. But, values of dilatation remained negative, reflecting probably lag of the biological repair of the inflammatory process the indicators of clinical remission.

